

NABI AS A REPRESENTATIVE OF THE DIDACTIC STYLE

Rahimova L.

Ph.D., Assoc. Prof.

Institute of Manuscripts named after Muhammad Fuzuli, ANAS

ORCID: 0000-0003-0952-4452

Abstract

In Islamic thought, the term “*hikma*” (wisdom) is used in contrast to philosophy and, according to dictionaries, carries meanings such as hidden thought, unknown cause, God’s concealed purpose in the creation of beings and events, and proverb, among others. In literature, the term is more commonly employed to denote a worldview grounded in life experience that reflects the general intellectual and moral norms of society. The primary aim of *hikemī* (didactic) poetry, which is based on this mode of thought, is to encourage the reader to reflect, to inform, and to guide individuals toward truth and the right path through reasoned contemplation. In fact, from our earliest written texts beginning with the Gokturk inscriptions through works such as Yusuf Has Hacib’s *Kutadgu Bilig*, political treatises (*siyāsatnāmes*), and the couplets and verses of *divans*, it is possible to observe didactic motifs centered on moral instruction and guidance. However, as a distinct literary path or movement, didactic-based *hikemī* style or *hakīmāne* poetry emerged in the seventeenth century.

Keywords: Yusuf Nabi, *hakīmāne*, didactic, classical, Turkish.

Introduction

One of the prominent representatives of this style and literary school in the seventeenth century was Yusuf Nabi of Urfa. In this regard, the scholar of Classical Turkish literature, Mine Mengi, notes the following: Nabi’s position as the founder of a literary school is a manifestation of his character, which is inclined toward reflection and encouraging others to think. Having set as his aim the articulation of ideas related to human beings, life, and society, as well as guiding indecisive individuals toward the right path and offering moral counsel, Nabi sought to convey these ideas through his poetry. [22;131] Even prior to Nabi, the *hakīmāne* (didactic–philosophical) poetic style can be observed in the quatrains (*rubai*’s) of Azimzade Haleti (1570–1631). Sources indicate that Haleti was among the intellectuals of his time and that he left behind a rich personal library. In accordance with his temperament, Haleti showed a preference for composing poetry in the *rubai* genre. In his quatrains, the poet articulated the deficiencies of the society in which he lived as well as its moral and social problems, reflecting his ideas and reflections in his poetry. Along the path opened by Nabi through the integration of poetry and thought, poets such as Sabit, Rami Mehmed Pasha, Sami, Seyyid Vehbi, Chelebızade Asim, Kodja Ragib Pasha, Diyarbakırlı Hami, Antakyalı Munif, and Reshid were also influenced by this literary movement. According to sources, Rami Mehmed Pasha who was a close friend of Nabi and one of the figures who laid the groundwork for the Treaty of Karlowitz, regarded as a crucial turning point in Turkish history reflected the deterioration of moral norms as well as the political and social conditions of his time in his poetry. Another poet in whose works we observe the century’s *hikemī* style expressed in a distinctive manner is Alaeddin Sabit from Bosnia (d. 1712). Sabit’s incorporation of elements from folk folklore, such as proverbs, idioms, and local expressions, into his poetry represents a significant innovation in Turkish poetry of that period. In addition to these features, his poetry also prominently employs contrasts, puns, simple expressions, and word-play. According to sources, Kodja Ragib Pasha can be

regarded as the most influential representative of this literary school after Nabi [20; 179].

Main part

The 17th century was a period of decline for the Ottoman state. Nabi lived during a time when various state institutions were disintegrating. Although this era witnessed political and administrative decline, literary progress and development were notable. During this century, Ottoman poets often compared themselves with Persian poets, emphasizing their own merits. In the second half of the century, the *Sebk-i Hindi* movement exerted an influence over poets such as Nef’i, Naili, and Nabi. During this period, Nef’i transformed the *qasida* by removing it from its traditional panegyric status and introducing a new atmosphere, while Nabi, by emphasizing thought and reflection in his poetry, created the *hikemī* style. According to sources, in the *qasida* genre, Nef’i and Nabi are recognized as leading figures; in the *ghazal*, Yahya Efendi; in the *rubai*, Azimzade Haleti; and in the *masnavi* genre, Nevizade Atai Usta.

Nabi, the founder of *hikemī* poetry, was born in Urfa in 1052/1642. Spending his childhood and youth there, he later moved to Istanbul, where he held various official positions. Following the death of his master, Musahip Mustafa Pasha, the poet was sent to Aleppo, where he spent twenty-five years of his life. It was also in Aleppo that he composed his famous works *Xeyriyye* and *Xeyrabat*. Nabi’s circumstances changed when Baltacı Mehmed Pasha was appointed Beylerbeyi of Aleppo. In his later years, Nabi returned to Istanbul together with Mehmed Pasha and, according to sources, passed away in 1712. His return to Istanbul was warmly welcomed among poets. In this regard, Bosnian poet Sabit expressed his pleasure at Nabi’s return to Istanbul alongside Mehmed Pasha in the *Ramazaniyye qasida* he composed for Baltacı Mehmed Pasha. In the following verses, Sabit praises Nabi as the creator of a new style and as a rare master of his craft:

Yüklēnbūd tazā qumāsh-i-Halebī-ma’nāy,
Gældī İstanbulā shāh-bandarī-tāxt-i-‘irfān.

Mūjīdī-wādīy-i-naw muhtārī-tarz-i-jadīd,

Mu-shikāf qalamī nādirah ustād-i-jahān. [31;87]

Providing information about Nabi's family, Prof. Dr. Masarrat Dirioz notes the following: 'His father was Seyid Mustafa; his grandfather, Seyid Mahmud; his great-grandfather, Seyid Mahmud Bakir; and his great-great-grandfather, Sheikh Ahmed Naqshbandi. His brothers were Hacı Mahmud Aga, Hacı Mehmed, and Seyid Ahmed. Hacı Mahmud's sons were Hacı Mehmed and İsmail. One of Nabi's sisters was known as Hacı Hemshire. Nabi's own sons were Abulkheyr Mehmed and Mehmed Amin.

[8;668-673]. Overall, Nabi's works should be examined within the context of the atmosphere of the period in which he lived, having witnessed the reigns of six sultans. Nabi was a figure deeply aware of the unrest and uncertainty of his time, the inefficiencies of state administration, and the social harm caused by widespread corruption among professionals, excessive attachment to wealth and property, hypocrisy, and the pursuit of personal gain in every matter. He sought, at least spiritually under the shadow of reason and wisdom, to live in relative peace [16; 56]. The following couplets, taken from the *cūlusiyah* qasida composed for the accession of Sultan Mahmud IV, provide insight into the state of the country during Nabi's lifetime:

Misāl-i-hāl-yi bī-mah-tab qalmūshdā,
Darūn-i-mulk hazīn tāxt-i-saltanat māghdūr.
Bū dūlatin yūgh idī bir tabīb-i-qamharī,
Mizāj-i-mamlakat ūmūshdā afiyāt-dūr.
Khārābā tutūsh idī yūz mazār-i-iqbal,
Riyāz-i-mamlakat qaplāmūsh idī mār u mūr.
Pūr idī sabzay-i-bīganā bā gulshan-i-dahr,
Ūtūrūsh idī hūmmālār maqām-i-usfur.
Natīja ne qadar jawr-i-tafrīqā bār īshā,
Sipīhr jūmlāsīn īkrādā nemūd qūsūr.

The state of the country saddens the observer. The sultanate has fallen prey to injustice. As the nation is in an unhealthy condition, there is no physician capable of restoring it. The fields of fortune and prosperity have been ruined, and the lands of the country have been overrun by ants and serpents. The world, once like a rose garden, has been overtaken by useless plants. The bird of fate, which should be the mythical Huma, has alighted instead as a mere sparrow. As a result, calamity has befallen the Ottoman Empire. [31;87].

Nabi was influenced by Firuddin Attar, who first introduced the *hikemī* poetic style and referred to his religious poems as 'wisdom'; by the Azerbaijani poet Saib Tabrizi; and by the Iranian poets Molla Jami and Shovketi-Bukhari. This influence is particularly evident in Nabi's divan composed in Persian. He became the representative in Anatolia of Saib's conception of poetry, adorned with reflection and wisdom. More broadly, didactic and wisdom-oriented ideas and motifs are reflected throughout the literature of the Near and Middle East, and Azerbaijani literature is no exception in this regard.

In the 17th century, Azerbaijani literature featured poems with didactic content and couplets or verses conveying moral and advisory ideas, even if these did not constitute an independent genre. Such themes are evident in the works of Muhammad Emmani, in Masihi's poem *Varqa and Gulshah*, in the poetry of Saib Tabrizi, in the *ghazals*, *qasidas*, *rubais*, and

single-couplet poems of Qovsi Tabrizi and Maczub Tabrizi, as well as in the lyrical works of poets such as Murtazagulu Khan Zafar and Vahid Qazvini. These works urge readers to live a well-ordered life, to appreciate the valuable blessings granted by God, and to make proper use of their youth. They advise against being driven by worldly wealth and material desires, encourage mutual assistance among people, advocate for wisdom, and warn against spending one's life solely for riches. These poets particularly emphasize doing good deeds, placing trust in the Creator, remaining undaunted by difficulties on the right path, working diligently, and recognizing that everyone will ultimately reap the consequences of their own actions. In his works, Nabi respectfully mentioned Azerbaijani poets such as Nizami, Khaghani, and Saib Tabrizi, and composed *taḥmis* (paraphrastic expansions) on the works of Fuzuli and Saib Tabrizi. The great Azerbaijani poet Fuzuli had a significant influence on Nabi, particularly evident in Nabi's *Qasideyi-'Ezliyye*, where the impact of Fuzuli's *Shikayāt-nāme* is clearly visible. [18].

Nabi produced numerous works in both prose and poetry. His divans in Turkish and Persian, the *masnavi Xeyriyye*, *Xeyrabad*, *Tercumeyi-Hadisi-Arbain*, and *Surname* were composed in verse, while works such as *Fetihnameyi-Kamaniche*, *Zeyli-siyeri-Veysi*, *Tohfetul-harameyn*, and *Munshaat* were written in prose. Among these, however, the two works in Turkish - the *Divan* and *Xeyriyye* - brought the poet the greatest fame. Nabi's poetic conception can be understood from certain couplets taken from his work *Xeyriyye*:

Hikmat-āmīz garkdūr ash-shar
Ki ma'ālī bulā irshādā medār.
Āb-i-ḥikmat-lā bulūr nawsh u namā,
Gulshan-i-shi'r u riyāz-i-inshā.

Poetry must be imbued with wisdom, for the purpose of poetry is to awaken the reader and guide them to the right path. When the rose garden of poetry and the field of prose are watered with the water of wisdom, what grows there will be nourished more fully [31; 86]. Nabi explained his interest in writing poetry as follows:

Tavajjuh nemēz idim shī'r-i Nābī-yā bī-hamd,
Bayān-i-sirr-i-ḥikām olmasāydī mazmūnū.

If the content of poetry did not contain the secrets of wisdom, I would not be so interested in it. In his work *Xeyriyye*, Nabi also criticizes the poetic approach of his contemporaries, reproaching them for writing poems focused solely on love and failing to bring any innovation to poetry.

Baxsān aksar suhān-i-shā'ir-i-khām,
Zulfu sunbul gülü bülbül mey-u jām.

Chıxamaz dā'ireyi-dilbar-dan,
Qadd-u hadd-u lab-u chashmi-tar-dan.

Gāh bahāra tolāshur gāh chamanā,
İlīshur sarv u gülü yāsamanā.

.....
Kechinur mātīy-i hayidā bilā,
Lafzi-mashhūr u jahān-dīdā bilā.

Ikī har-vārdur ū beyti-du-tā,
Kolmāya tazā qumāsh-i-ma'nā.

Examining the poems of inexperienced poets, we observe that they focus on hair, ears of grain, roses, nightingales, wine, and cups. They speak of the beloved's neck, mole, lips, or eyes. Their poems mention spring, cypress, and jasmine. By merely repeating what has already been said, they attempt to navigate poetic expression. Their couplets, like two burdened donkeys, carry old meanings instead of weaving new ones. Nabi placed great emphasis on poetry as a means of effectively conveying ideas to people. This is evident from certain couplets in his work *Xeyriyye*:

Tiz farāmūsh olunur nasr suhān,
Nazm ammā ki edar dowri-dehān.

While what is conveyed in prose is quickly forgotten, poetry circulates orally and remains in memory for a long time. However, not every work written in verse, which we call poetry, is easily retained in memory. The most essential condition for this is that the poetry must be harmonious:

Suhān ūl dānlu khūsh-āyandā garkdūr ki ānī,
Edanā naw-i-bashar bālkī malā'ik azbar.

Poetry must be melodious to the ear in order to be memorized, not only humans, but also angels, can commit to memory poetry that is pleasing in sound. [31;89].

Within his Turkish *divan*, Nabi included *ghazals* and *taḥmis* in Persian. His work *Tercumei-Hadisi-Arbain* is a Turkish metrical translation of Molla Jami's *Translation of Forty Hadiths*. Influenced by Firuddin Attar's *Ilāhīnāme*, his *Xeyrabat* is a *masnavi* composed in a lyrical, romantic style. The *Surname*, which recounts the circumcision ceremonies of Sultan Mahmud IV's sons, is particularly valuable for reflecting the social, political, and historical conditions of its time. As in his poetic works, Nabi also demonstrated remarkable literary prowess in his prose compositions. For instance, in his *Fetihnameyi-Kamaniche*, the poet conveyed his impressions of Sultan Mahmud IV's campaign to the Kingdom of Poland (Lehistan) and the capture of the Kamianets fortress. This work was published in Istanbul in 1865. The work *Tohfatul-Harameyn* recounts Nabi's impressions during his pilgrimage (Hajj). *Zeyli-siyeri Veysi* consists of Nabi's additions to the prose work of the 7th-century author Veysi, which covers events from the birth of Prophet Muhammad to the Battle of Badr. Nabi's *Münshaat* comprises his official and personal correspondence. As noted above, Nabi's *Divan* remains the work that brought him his greatest renown. Manuscripts of Urfa-born Yusuf Nabi's works are preserved in hundreds in libraries around the world, particularly in Switzerland, the United Kingdom, Russia, and especially in Turkey. The *Catalogue of Manuscript Divans of Istanbul Libraries* provides information on the Turkish copies of Nabi's works. Of the 35 Istanbul manuscripts, two were copied during the author's lifetime; 11 are dated and 24 are undated. The dated manuscripts:

1)H.1108 (1696/97) – Istanbul University Library, T.5575/5/1 2)H.1112 (1700) – Istanbul University Library, 3)H.1125 (1713) – Topkapı Palace Museum (Treasury Library) – 857, 4) H.1136 (1724) – Topkapı Palace Museum (Emanet Library) – 1634 5) H.1138 (1725) – Köprülü Library (Asim Bey) – 426 6)H.1139 (1726) – Süleymaniye Library (Hamdiyya) – 1117 7)H.1148 (1736) – Topkapı Palace Museum (Treasury

– 954 8)H.1153 (1740) – Ragib Pasha Library – 1113 9)H.1170 (1756) – Süleymaniye Library (Halet Efendi) – 683 10)H.1170 (1757) – Süleymaniye Library (Yahya Tevfik Efendi) – 306 11)H.1187 (1773) – Süleymaniye Library (Hafiz Efendi) – 940

At the Institute of Manuscripts named after Muhammad Fuzuli of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences five copies of three of this renowned poet's works have been identified across four manuscript volumes.

In the manuscript of the *Divan* with the code B-5215, 499 *ghazals*, 29 *rubais*, *qitas*, and *taḥmis* on Bakhai's poems by Nabi are included. The manuscript consists of 122 folios and measures 15×20.5, with the text area being 9×16. Each page contains 17 lines of verse. It is unbound. The text is written in *nastaliq* script with black ink on European paper. The paper bears a watermark dating from the 8th century (Hijri). The scribe was Muhammad Sadiq al-Vani, and the copy was completed in 1164/1750. On folio 1b, there is a note indicating that this manuscript belonged to Mehdi, the son of Haji Hasan Kamarli, a teacher of the Iravan school. The manuscript begins as follows:

الغاضبين معاني به خاندن بو
Al-Qāzīdan ma'ānīyē khāndir,
الدمع من العين الى الحال دلسل
It ends with a couplet.

The work *Xeyriyye*, written in Aleppo by Nabi for his son Abulkheyr Mehmed, is a didactic piece that addresses how his son should live as a virtuous and happy member of society. Through his son, Nabi also offers guidance to the youth of his time, aiming to show them the right path. The work is particularly valuable for its portrayal of the historical and social conditions of the period, often with elements of satire. *Xeyriyye* is composed in the meter *fā'ilātun fā'ilātun fā'ilātun fā'ilun*.

Copies of the work *Kitabi-Xeyriyye* are held at the Institute of Manuscripts of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences (ANAS). The manuscript with the code B-5215 consists of 54 folios, measuring 15×20.5, with a text area of 9×16. The manuscript is unbound, and each page contains 17 lines of verse. The work was first printed in 1252/1841 under the title *Kulliyati-Nabi* at the Bulaq Press and was printed a second time in 1307/1889 at the lithography of Abu Ziya. The text is written in *nastaliq* script with black ink on European paper, which bears an 8th century watermark. On folio 178ab, there is a *taḥmis* composed by Nabi for the poet Sidqi, in which he employed eight couplets from Nasimi. The scribe was Muhammad Sadiq al-Vani, and the manuscript was copied in 1196/1781.

The manuscript begins as follows:

حمد اول الله عظيم الشانه
Hamd ol Allāhi-'Azīm-i-'Alīshānā

بر فاتحه در رجای نالی

It is a *Fātiḥah*, composed by Rijā'i-Nabi.

It ends with a couplet.

A manuscript of the religious and moral *masnavi* that Nabi wrote over fifty years for his son Abdu'l al-Khayr Muhammad Chelebi is preserved at the Institute of Manuscripts under the code B-4321. This manuscript is registered under the title *Nasihatname*. Consisting of 51 folios, it measures 16×22, with 15–16 lines per page.

Bound in a green cardboard cover, the work is contained between folios 45a–96b. The text is written in *nastaliq* script with black ink on white paper, arranged in two columns. There are 25 headings, distinguished in red ink. The manuscript was copied in 1260/1844.

The scribe is احمد بن محمود افندی نعمت ابادی Ahmed bin Mahmud Efendi Nematabadi.

The work begins as follows:

حمد اول الله عظيم الشانه

Hamd ol Allāhi-‘Azīm-i-‘Alīshānā

It ends.

خير ايده حضرت حق انجامك

Xeyr edə Hazrat-i Haqq anjāmın

Two copies of the prose work *Tohfatul-Harameyn* by the poet are preserved at the Institute of Manuscripts named after Muhammad Fuzuli of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences (ANAS). One of these is the manuscript coded B-7406. The 70-folio manuscript is bound in brown leather and measures 11.5×20.5. Each page contains 20 lines of text, which is written in *nastaliq* script.

The work begins as follows:

ای بیت حرامی صف غفرانه مقام

Ey beyti-harāmi, safi-qafrāna maqām (1b)

بو تحفه حرمینم قبول ایده مولى تمت الكتاب

It ends. ... Bu *Töhfeyi-Hərameynin* qəbül eylə Mövlā. Tammat al-kitāb (68a-b)

The second manuscript is coded B-321. It measures 14×20 cm and consists of 57 folios, bound in a red leather cover. The manuscript bears a seal dated 1158 belonging to a person named Ismail. It is contained in the same volume as Abu-Nasr Farahi’s *Nisabus-Sibyan*. The text was copied in *nastaliq* script in 1128/1715.

The work begins as follows:

ای بیت حرامی صف غفرانه مقام

It ends.

بو تحفه حرمینم قبول ایده مولى تمت الكتاب

فی سنه ۱۱۲۸

Conclusion

Nabi’s oeuvre occupies a significant place in the literary history of Azerbaijan and the Ottoman Empire. His works, composed in both verse and prose, present a rich content that aims to stimulate thought and guide readers toward the right path through didactic and wisdom-oriented motifs. The manuscript copies preserved at the Institute of Manuscripts named after Muhammad Fuzuli of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences (ANAS), particularly those in Baku, provide valuable primary sources for studying Nabi’s creativity. In works such as the *Divan*, *Xeyriyye*, *Tohfatul-Harameyn*, and others, guidance, wisdom, and moral precepts are emphasized, reflecting the socio-political conditions of his time while also influencing the development of Azerbaijani literature. Nabi considered showing the right path to both the youth of his era and humanity in general as a central aim, and through his stylistic innovations in poetry and prose, he established a literary school. The wisdom-laden and didactic content of his works remains a valuable literary heritage for contemporary readers and scholars alike.

Nabi’s oeuvre is remarkably rich and engaging. In particular, the copies of his works preserved at the Institute of Manuscripts named after Muhammad Fuzuli of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences (ANAS) make the study of this esteemed poet’s creativity, based on the manuscripts held in Baku, highly significant and timely.

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